

Review of *Technocolonialism: Digital Innovation and Humanitarian Practice*

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The book *Technocolonialism: Digital Innovation and Humanitarian Practice* provides an ambitious and timely analysis of the intersection between digital technologies, humanitarian action, and ongoing forms of technological colonialism. This review interrogates the book's relevance, theoretical engagement, and its dialogue with debates in this field.

Madianou's concept of "technocolonialism" captures the transformation of humanitarianism into a fragmented yet infrastructurally unified field, where extraction and experimentation with data reproduce structural and epistemic violence across global divides. The arguments presented are especially pertinent to the evolving landscape in which algorithmic systems, biometric technologies, and data-driven governance increasingly shape humanitarian decision-making. The focus on structural violence and datafication resonates with recent critiques, which warn international agencies about the risks of algorithmic bias, exclusion, and the creation of new vulnerabilities arising from data-driven interventions. Madianou's attention to everyday resistance and the inadequacy of feedback mechanisms in humanitarian settings underscores urgent dilemmas faced by practitioners.

This book raises concerns about the lack of public accountability, the opacity of data-sharing agreements, and the potential risks to privacy and data safeguarding in such public-private partnerships. The text critiques the "data promise" in humanitarian contexts, emphasizes uneven access to digital infrastructures, and highlights the risks of exclusion or excessive surveillance. Importantly, Madianou situates this violence within the historical genealogy of humanitarian action, demonstrating continuities between imperial projects of domination and contemporary technical infrastructures. Her manuscript illustrates how platforms like WFP's Hunger Map Live and partnerships with private entities, such as Palantir, render populations legible and governable while amplifying vulnerability to exclusion and opacity. Critical engagement with structural violence, infrastructural violence, and the entanglements of humanitarian organizations with state and market logic highlights how objectivity claims surrounding AI and digital tools conceal profound power asymmetries and deny meaningful accountability.

Madianou's work puts lived experience at the center —an essential corrective in debates often dominated by technical and donor-centric perspectives. The book presents complex theoretical arguments in clear and evocative prose, striking a balance between scholarly rigor and anecdotal storytelling. The introduction and subsequent chapters incorporate personal fieldwork, vivid illustrations, such as artist Zach Blas's "Face Cages", and a range of accessible examples, from biometric identity systems to chatbots in refugee camps. The writing is engaging for both academic and practitioner audiences.

The author demonstrates deep engagement with foundational and recent works, too —citing postcolonial theory (Fanon, 1961; Said, 1978), Black radical traditions (Patterson, 2022; Robinson, 2021), critical data studies (Couldry & Mejias, 2019; Eubanks, 2017), and studies of structural violence (Farmer, 2004, 2005; Gupta, 2012). It traces the history of humanitarianism

and colonialism and places the technocolonialism framework in dialogue with parallel concepts. At the same time, the text remains sensitive to ethnographic nuance and the importance of multi-sited research (Marcus, 1995; Pink et al., 2016).

While the bibliography is impressively wide-ranging, a potential underdeveloped area emerges. The book demonstrates how everyday resistance and local appropriation manifest through "mundane resistance," such as non-participation in digital feedback systems and the repurposing of humanitarian radio. Examples like Dina and Carol's SMS activism after Typhoon Haiyan and the use of radio for storytelling shed light on grassroots interventions. It also documents activist projects, including Torn Apart / Separados, for exposing immigrant detention sites and Mexican feminicide data-mapping platforms that confront official silence around gender violence. Additionally, hashtag activism and digital witnessing, such as #Moria6, are presented as forms of resistance addressing anti-refugee discourse and police violence. Nevertheless, the book primarily treats these instances as illustrations of resistance rather than as models of bottom-up data activism. The discussion of indigenous data sovereignty and justice movements is brief, although the book acknowledges the empowering potential of digital technologies for recognizing the local knowledge of marginalized communities. This suggests that greater focus on sustained grassroots initiatives and more detailed accounts of activist-run data infrastructures could further demonstrate how alternatives can challenge extractive data regimes. By more fully engaging with organized activist governance practices, its arguments could move beyond seeing activism as reactive, instead highlighting how grassroots actors proactively offer pathways for decolonial data practice.

This review is attentive to the challenges outlined by Madianou, not only as matters of theoretical interest, but as core concerns that have shaped my own trajectory. My engagement with the complexities of digital humanitarianism began with my doctoral dissertation (2017), which examined the transformative possibilities and ambiguities of data-driven interventions. Subsequent work (e.g., 2018, 2022) further investigated how data technologies intensify risks within humanitarian and development contexts. Most recently, I have addressed the opacity, embedded biases, and injustice in autonomous decision-making systems (2024). This positioning informs my reading of *Technocolonialism* and underscores the stakes of the open peer commentary model adopted by *Dialogues on Digital Society*.

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